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The Editor-in-Chief

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**Mediating Role of Drug Use History in the Relationship Between Clinical Personality
Patterns and Criminal Behaviour**

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Abstract

The study examined the mediating role of drug use history in the relationship between clinical personality patterns and Criminal Behaviour (CB) among convicted inmates of Nigeria correctional institution (Oke-Kura) Ilorin, Kwara. A total of 450 convicted inmates participated in the study. Their age range is 18-25 years. The study employed ex post facto research design and purposive sampling techniques. The result revealed that drug use history significantly predicts criminal behaviour [$f(2;375) = 11.438, p < .01$], while the post-hoc result presented shows that respondents with a drug use history had the highest level of criminal behaviour ($M = 24.39; SD = 8.512$). The clinical personality patterns significantly predict criminal behaviour ($R = .354; R^2 = .126; F(11) = 3.879; P < .001$). The drug use history as a mediating factor significantly predicts the relationship between clinical personality patterns and criminal behaviour ($b = .06, t = 3.682, p < .01$). This study also revealed that clinical personality patterns predict criminal behaviour ($b = .008, t = -5.12; p < .001$). It was concluded that drug use history mediates between clinical personality patterns and criminal behaviour.

Keyword: Criminal behaviour, Clinical personality patterns, Drug use history

Introduction

The spate of criminal behaviour is on the increase in Nigeria and is becoming worrisome, the concept of criminal behaviour varies among scholars (Önal Dölek & Adeleke, 2023). Crime is a global challenge, not limited to Nigeria. America is a nation that is concerned about crime at all times (Tonry, 2023). A survey conducted in 1994 even revealed that Americans considered crime as their greatest concern, even more than the economy, employment, and unemployment as a whole (Schaefer & Lamm, 1997). In Nigeria, there is a rapid crime issue that is indigenous to the country (Enemuwe et al., 2025).

In Nigeria, crime remains a persistent and challenging issue. Both sophisticated and violent offenses continue to rise, making it difficult to apprehend perpetrators, while victims often receive minimal support. Certain regions face particularly severe challenges, with the Niger Delta and northern Nigeria experiencing heightened levels of crime (Umanah et al., 2023). In the Niger Delta, violence intensified as youths became involved in conflicts surrounding the oil industry (Garba, 2017). The impact of crime goes deep. Crime in Nigeria also results in loss of life, injuries, destruction of property, and huge financial losses (Oluwakayode et al., 2024). Stealing cars, muggings and burglaries amount to billions of dollars and the emotional cost cannot be quantified. (Adekoya and Abdul-Razak, 2021). Criminal behaviour includes detected offenses (Swaab & Meynen, 2023) which can be categorized into: reckless behavior, conflict with authority, covert delinquency (Swaab & Meynen, 2023), A general factor, such as general deviance or antisocial syndrome, can explain these factors. The distinction between these factors is important to understand deviance.

Criminal behaviour is linked to behaviors that are reinforced more than conforming actions. It can be explained sociologically, anthropologically, or biologically (Ling et al., 2019). Some behaviors stem from biological factors like personality, genetics, or brain damage. Paternal violence, poverty, single-parent families, and rough areas also play a role (Gutek, 2001; Schraiber & Edge, 2024). Studies show a link between drug use and crime in countries like the US (Cabrera, 1999) and the UK (Bennett, 2000). In Nigeria, drug studies often focus on abuse (Oweibia et al., 2025). This study examines drug use as a social problem and its relationship to crime among youth in Ilorin, Kwara State.

Lagos, Nigeria's most populous city, has seen an increase in street children, which may cause more drug use (Dada et al., 2016; Jatau et al., 2021). There is need for more data on drug use in Kwara (Igwe et al., 2009). Drug use trends are changing quickly (Nawi et al., 2021; Jatau et

al., 2021). Nigeria's cannabis use is over 14%, which is the highest in Africa (El Moubchiri et al., 2024; Odeigah et al., 2025). Cocaine and opiate use rates are also high compared to other African countries (Africa, n.d.). Youth drug use increases when access to drugs is unrestricted. (Abdullahi, 2019). Methamphetamine labs were discovered in Lagos in 2010 and 2012 (Johnson et al., 2022). Many drug users are not aware of the risks. (Olanrewaju et al., 2022; Onwubiko, 2012). Amphetamine, cannabis, alcohol, and multiple substance use have links to crime (Håkansson & Jesionowska, 2018). Drug-related crimes range from violence to theft (Håkansson & Jesionowska, 2018; Flamini et al., 2021; Rafeaie et al., 2013; Barati, 2025). Personality disorders and addictive disorders like antisocial personality disorder (APD) lead to a higher risk of crime (McGrath and Reynolds, 2024; Filov, 2019). Eysenck (1983) established that psychoticism, extroversion and neuroticism are associated with antisocial behaviour.

Research suggests that certain personality traits, as measured by the Big Five model, are linked to criminal behavior. Low conscientiousness and low agreeableness are associated with impulsivity and aggression, while high neuroticism can increase emotional instability, all of which may contribute to offending tendencies. (Clark et al., 2007). Aggression, impulsiveness and narcissism are associated with crime. Extroversion and neuroticism were associated with self-destructive behavior (Schmalleger, 2008; Eysenck andamp; Eysenck, 1985).

Similar terms include antisocial personality, psychopathy and sociopath. Sociopaths are caused by unhealthy living conditions, and psychopaths by inner issues (Fisher et al., 2024; Mariano, 2025). The antisocial personality is low guilt, charisma, cleverness, violations, non-relationships, impulsivity, risk-taking, cold-hearted, and shallow emotions (Mariano, 2025). Causes include traumatic socialization, neurological issues, and brain problems (Mariano, 2025). Low arousal may incite thrill-seeking behaviour.

Objectives of the study

This study aimed to investigate the relationship between drug use history and clinical personality patterns as predictors of criminal behaviour among convicted inmate of Nigeria correctional institution. The specific objective includes:

1. To identify that drug use history contributes to criminal behaviour among convicted inmate.

2. To establish that clinical personality patterns contribute to criminal behaviour among convicted inmate.
3. To explore that drug use history will mediate the relationship between clinical personality patterns and criminal behaviour among convicted inmate.

Research Hypothesis

H1. Drug use history will significantly predict criminal behavior among convicted inmates.

H2: Clinical personality patterns will significantly predict criminal behavior among convicted inmates.

H3: Drug use history will mediate the relationship between clinical personality patterns and criminal behavior among convicted inmates.

Methods

Research approach

This study employed the use of the quantitative research approach as it allows for the identification of patterns, testing the hypotheses that allows for drawing a conclusion that extend beyond the original sample and the determination of the direction of the relationship between variables across a larger sample (Bhandari, 2022).

Research design

This study uses an expo facto research design. It assists the researcher to test hypotheses about relationships on existing data in which the characteristics of human participants cannot be manipulated. This design enables the research to determine if addicted drug users or non-drug users are prone to criminal behaviour or clinical personality patterns have a contribution to criminal behaviour and drug use history as a mediator between clinical personality patterns and criminal behaviour.

Participants

Four hundred and fifty inmates (450) aged 18 and above, from the Ilorin partake in the study. Target populations for this study are strictly convicted inmates in the prison of oke-kura correctional institution Ilorin, kwara state. All participants were volunteers, and all are informed about the research and the objective of the research.

Sampling techniques

The sampling technique that was adopted, is the purposive sampling procedure, this is a subjective selection of a sample that suits the purpose of the research or that satisfies the judgement of the research as being representative of the population, i.e., the questionnaire was only administered to the inmate in Oke-Kura Ilorin custodian centre.

Instruments

Data were collected using a well-structured questionnaire administered to prisoners. The questionnaire would consist of a standardised scale with accepted properties. Three scales were used; drug abuse screening test (DAST), MCMI-III, and Brief criminal attitude scale. The instrument was designed to collect information on the demographic characteristics of the respondent as well as the psychological variable in the study.

Checklist for Inclusion Criteria

Inclusion criteria: The participants in this study were convicted inmates currently serving sentences in Nigeria correctional institution (Oke-Kura) Ilorin, Kwara. Only individuals with a documented history of drug use were included. All participants provided informed consent to take part in the study. The study was limited to adults aged 18-25 years and including both male and female inmates.

Exclusion criteria: Participants were excluded from this study if they were not convicted inmates or had no documented history of drug use. Individuals who had not undergone assessment for clinical personality patterns were also excluded. Additionally, inmates who did not provide informed consent or were below/above the specified age range of [18-25] were not included in the study.

Section A: Participant Background

This section records participant's details, like age, education, job history, gender, marital status, religion, tribal background.

Section B: Drug Abuse Screening Test (DAST)

Dr. Harvey A. Skinner from the Addiction Research Foundation, Toronto, Canada (now the Centre for Addiction and Mental Health), created and tested the Drug Abuse Screening Test (DAST).

Section C: Million Clinical Multiaxial inventory (MCMI-III)

This scale measures how personality can contribute to criminal behaviour, the scale has different subtypes in which the personality scale was adopted from the whole, which will measure 11 personality patterns. This scale in this study was only measure eleven (11) personalities, which include antisocial, avoidant, compulsive, depressive, dependent, histrionic, narcissistic, masochistic, sadistic and negativistic schizoid. This scale was developed by Theodore Millon 1994, PHD.DSC, the scale consists of 175 items, of which this research adopts 107 items which measure for clinical personality, for which responses are “true” or “false”. with Cronbach's alpha of .89.89. Craig, 2008).

Section D: Brief Criminal Attitude Scale

This scale uses a simple True/False format. People taking it respond to 15 statements, and there are no correct answers. The statements show opinions that some people have. Created by Taylor, 1968 the scale measures criminal attitudes and can show changes in attitude after things like treatment. It proved useful in a group therapy experiment with inmates, where it helped measure progress before and after therapy. With .076 as the Cronbach's alpha.

Procedure

This study employed a standardized questionnaire survey, the questionnaire requires participants to fill up sections, which include drug use history, clinical personality patterns (independent variable) and criminal behaviour(dependent variable). This questionnaire was administered to those who are willing to meet up the criteria of interest of study.

Ethical considerations

The ethical issues that were relevant to the study were properly considered and observed. A formal approval of Ilorin Custodian Center was conferred before the study began. Then, the respondents were to make their oral informed consent following an elaborate briefing about the purpose of the study and informed that their answers would be anonymous and confidential. In the process of conducting the surveys, the participants were given clear guidelines on the

purpose of the survey and how it would be conducted. Their involvement was voluntary, and the participants were allowed to withdraw at their will. After the administration of informed consent, questionnaires were given out.

Results

The 450 respondents who participated in this study, involved prison inmates of the correctional home in Ilorin Kwara state Nigeria. The age ranged from 18-25 years 20(4.4), 22-25years 73(16.2%) 26-29 years: 3 (0.7%); 30-33 years: 165 (36.7%); 34-37 years: 53 (11.8%); and 38 and above years: 136 (30.2%). Regarding the gender of the respondents, 423 (94.0%) were males and 27 (6.0%) females. The Christian participants were 244 (54.3%), Muslims were 197 (43.8%), and 3 (1.3%) were from other religions. The tribe of respondents: Yoruba 327 (72.7%), Igbo 41 (9.1%), Hausa/Fulani 59(13.1%) and another tribe 21 (4.7%). Their educational level in school was SSCE 126 (28.0%), OND 132 (29.3%), HND 87 (19.3%), BSC 90(20.0%) and MSC 15 (3.3%). Concerning marital status, about half of the participants (224, or 49.8%) were single. A little over a third (168, or 37.3%) were married, and around 13% (58 individuals) were divorced. For their working experiences, 239 (53.1%) have less than 5 years and 207 (46.0%) have 6-10 years.

Table 1 : Respondent Socio-demographics (n=450)

Variables	Category	Frequency	Percent(%)
Age (Years)	18-21	20	4.4
	22-25	73	16.2
	30-33	165	36.7
	34-37	53	11.8
	38 and above	136	30.2
Gender	Male	423	94.0
	Female	27	6.0
Religion	Christianity	244	54.2
	Islam	197	43.8
	Others	3	1.3
Educational	SSCE	126	28.0
	OND	132	29.3
	HND	87	19.3
	BSC	90	20.0
	MSC	15	3.3
Tribe	Yoruba	327	72.7
	Igbo	41	9.1

Marital Status	Hausa	59	13.1
	Other	21	4.7
	Single	224	49.8
	Married	168	37.3
	Divorced	58	12.9
Working experience			
	Less than 5 years	239	53.1
	6-10	207	46.0

Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis One

There will be significant influence of drug use history on criminal behaviour. We tested this idea using one way ANOVA, and the result presented on Table 4.

Table 2: How levels of drug use history affect criminal behaviour

Source	SS	df	MS	F	P
Between Groups	363.611	2	181.805	11.438	.000
Within Groups	5960.434	37515	.894		
Total	6324	.045	377		

Dependent variable: criminal behaviour

In order to ascertain the significant effect of hypothesis 1, which states that drug use history will be a predictor of criminal behaviour among convicted inmates, one-way ANOVA was used. The result shows that there is a significant link between drug use history and criminal behavior. $[F(2; 375) = 11.438, p < .01]$.

Table 3: Drug Use History and Criminal Conduct in Convicted Inmates: A Summary

Groups	N	M	SD	1	2	3
1. No Drug use history	136	21.94	3.115	1		
2 Drug use history	54	24.39	8.512	-2.447*	1	
3 Addiction	186	21.45	2.067	.4904	.6162*	1

Note: *p < 0.5; **Dependent variable:** criminal behaviour

The post-hoc result presented shows that respondents with a drug use history had the highest level of criminal behaviour (M = 24.39; SD = 8.512), then respondents with no drug use history (M = 21.94; SD = 3.115) and respondents with addiction (M = 21.45; SD = 2.067).

Hypothesis Two

Clinical personality patterns will be a predictor of criminal behavior among convicted inmate. We tested this hypothesis using multiple regressions and the results presented in Table 4.

Table 4.: Summary of Multiple Regressions showing the effect clinical personality patterns on criminal behaviour among convicted inmate

Variable	β	t	Sig	F	R	R ²
Schizoid	-.129	-1.682	0.94	3.879	.354a	.126
Antisocial	-.064	-.600	.549			
Sadistic	.069	.701	.484			
Compulsive	.021	.199	.842			
Negative	-.123	-1.243	.215			
Masochistic	.073	.791	.429			

Avoidant	-.014	-.154	.898
Depressive	.139	1.506	.133
Dependent	.159	1.927	.055
Historic	-.341	-3.250	.001
Narcissistic	-.060	-.536	.593

The results in table 4 showed that schizoid, antisocial, sadistic, compulsive, negative, masochistic, avoidant, depressive, dependent, historic, and narcissistic will jointly predict criminal behaviour ($R = .354$; $R^2 = .126$; $F(11) = 3.879$; $P < .001$). This implies that schizoid, antisocial, sadistic, compulsive, negative, masochistic, avoidant, depressive, dependent, historic, and narcissistic jointly accounted for 1% variance in criminal behaviour, while the remaining 99% could be attributed to other variables not considered in this study. However, the analysis of the independent predictions indicated that schizoid ($\beta = -.129$; $t = -1.682$; $P < 0.01$), sadistic ($\beta = .069$; $t = .701$; $P < .05$), negative ($\beta = -.123$; $t = -1.243$; $P < .02$), masochistic ($\beta = -.073$; $t = .791$; $P < .04$), depressive ($\beta = -.139$; $t = 1.506$; $P < .01$), dependent ($\beta = -.159$; $t = 1.927$ $P < .005$), historic ($\beta = -.341$; $t = -3.250$; $P < .001$) predicted significant effects on criminal behaviour. Therefore, the stated hypothesis is supported by the result obtained, and it is accepted that some personalities, such as schizoid, sadistic, negative, masochistic, depressive, dependent, and historic personalities, have a significant effect on criminal behaviour, while antisocial, compulsive, avoidant, and narcissistic personalities have no significant effect on criminal behaviour.

Hypothesis Three

There will be mediating role of drug use history between clinical personality patterns and criminal behaviour. The hypothesis was tested using regression analysis and was presented on Table 5 and Figure 1 respectively.

Figure 1 Caption: Mediation model.

Dependent variable: criminal behavior

Table 5: Bias-Corrected unstandardized, 95% Confidence Interval for the Indirect Effect of drug use history on criminal behaviour

Variables	LL	UL	BE	t	R	R ²	F	b	Sig.
A-Path				9.788	.5029	.2529	95.8	.28	.0001
B-Path				3.682	.2999	.0899	13.9	.06	.0003
C'-Path	-.007	.027	.005						
(Indirect)									
C-Path	-.0595	-.0265	-5.12					.0008	.0001

***p < .001, **p < .01

The result revealed that drug use history has a significant predictive clinical personality pattern, $b=.28$, $t=9.788$, $p<.001$, indicating that drug use history mediates between clinical personality patterns and criminal behaviour. Also, drug use history (the mediator) has a significant effect on criminal behaviour ($b=.06$, $t=3.682$, $p<.01$); while on the other hand, the direct effect states that there is a significant effect of clinical personality patterns on criminal behaviour ($b=.008$, $t=-5.12$, $p<.001$). This can be explained by the fact that clinical personality patterns were a significant predictor of criminal behaviour.

Recall the regression analysis showed that clinical personality patterns were a significant predictor of criminal behaviour. while controlling for drug use history (mediator), the result of

the second regression analysis shows that clinical personality patterns were a significant predictor of criminal behaviour. Meanwhile, the result of the indirect effect based on 5000 bootstrap samples shows that there was an indirect relationship between clinical personality patterns and criminal behaviour mediated by drug use history ($a*b = .015$, bootstrap = .007 and .027). on the other hand, there was a statistically direct effect between clinical personality patterns and criminal behaviour ($b=.0008$, $t= -5.12$ $p< .001$).

Preacher and Hayes (2004) say that in Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), a necessary component of mediation is a statistically and practically significant indirect effect. Table 5 shows that indirect relationship between the clinical personality patterns and criminal behaviour. The table shows that the indirect effect is .0155 with a 95% bootstrap confidence interval of .007 (lower limit) to .027 (upper limit).

Discussion

The study investigates drug use history in the relationship between clinical personality patterns and criminal behaviour among convicted inmate in Ilorin, Kwara state. Hypothesis one state that drug use history will significantly predict criminal behaviour. This research further indicates that the level of drug use history has an effect on level of criminal behaviour among inmate. This is in line with the study of (Hakansson & Jesionowska, 2018) which show that criminal justice client with substance use problem have played an importance role in increment of criminality several other report. Johnson et al., (2018) This study looks at how drug abuse affects crime among young people in Lagos, Nigeria. it's also concluded that drug abuse induced predatory crimes are common among adolescents. They concluded in their research that drug use history predicts criminal behaviour. Lammers et al. (2014) the study examine substance use and criminality and concluded that substance use or drug use is a predictor of criminality.

The second hypothesis state that clinical personality patterns will predict criminal behaviour. The result show that clinical personality patterns predicted criminal behaviour. In line with the study of Sinha, (2016) conclude that personality correlate with criminals. Also, Reid et al., (2021) the study show that personality is a also a predictor of criminal behaviour.

The third hypothesis states that a person's history of using drugs will explain the relationship between their personality and whether they engage in criminal actions. The results, as shown in Olaseni Abayomi O's (2025) study, indicate that a history of drug use affects how clinical

personality patterns and criminal actions relate to each other. Also, even without the mediating factor the clinical personality patterns also predict criminal behaviour. (Albery, 2003)

Recommendation

Based on the study's findings, we recommended that:

1. Campaigns and creating of awareness against drug use should be incorporated in health education curricula for all educational level
2. Enlightenment program should be organized from time to time so as to encourage the citizen of the country to channel their youthful energy into more productive, constructive and positive enterprises that could enhance their general wellbeing
3. More trained and educated psychologist should be employed in all correctional facilities and in psychiatrist home to help in rendering of psychotherapy for both clinical problem and crime justices
4. Lastly, the government should create a rule that forces ads for illegal drugs to tell people about the substance's health risks.

Conclusion

This research work examined drug use history in the relationship between clinical personality patterns and criminal behaviour among convicted inmates in Ilorin kwara state. Thus, it could be concluded from the findings of the study that drug use history significantly predicts criminal behaviour. The result shows that clinical personality patterns significantly predict criminal behaviour. Moreover, other research conducted has different results. The research brings awareness of some personality patterns that predict criminal behaviour among convicted inmates, in which the personality patterns include schizoid, sadistic, historic, masochistic, negative, depressive, and dependent, which significantly predict criminal behaviour among convicted inmates.

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